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РАЗДЕЛ. ЕСТЕСТВЕННЫЕ НАУКИ

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**MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF THE PROCESS OF CLEANING
NATURAL GASES FROM SULFUR COMPOUNDS**

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Annotation: In the example of the process of purification of natural gas from hydrogen sulfide by adsorption with the help of synthetic CaA zeolite, the issues of building a mathematical model and identifying its parameters were considered. The possibility of analytical solution of the mass transfer equations in the isothermal case for the adsorption process in the internal diffusion field has been determined, which allows to simplify the solution of the problem to a certain extent. Absorption processes of harmful mixtures from natural gases in solid adsorbents are of great interest in chemical technology. Analysis of their working conditions (both mathematical and physical), new theoretical and practical directions for more complete study and control of similar processes are emerging. However, despite the existence of a large number of laboratory and project studies in this field, systematic studies on the complex modeling and systematic analysis of the absorption purification of natural gases from sulfurous compounds are still lacking.

Keywords: adsorbent, adsorption, natural gas, zeolite, mathematical model

МАТЕМАТИЧЕСКАЯ МОДЕЛЬ ПРОЦЕССА ОЧИСТКИ ПРИРОДНЫХ ГАЗОВ ОТ СЕРОСОЕДИНЕНИЙ

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Аннотация: На примере процесса очистки природного газа от сероводорода адсорбцией с помощью синтетического цеолита СаА рассмотрены вопросы построения математической модели и определения ее параметров. Определена возможность аналитического решения уравнений массопереноса в изотермическом случае для процесса адсорбции в поле внутренней диффузии, что позволяет в определенной степени упростить решение задачи. Процессы абсорбции вредных смесей из природных газов твердыми адсорбентами представляют большой интерес в химической технологии. Анализ условий их работы (как математических, так и физических), появляются новые теоретические и практические направления для более полного изучения и управления подобными процессами. Однако, несмотря на наличие большого количества лабораторных и проектных исследований в этой области, до сих пор отсутствуют систематические исследования по комплексному моделированию и системному анализу процессов абсорбционной очистки природных газов от сернистых соединений.

Ключевые слова: адсорбент, адсорбция, природный газ, цеолит, математическая модель

Taking into account the above, researches were conducted in the field of building mathematical models of the processes considered in the work. The analyzed experimental studies allowed to come to the following

conclusion. It can be noted with great probability that these processes refer to internal diffusion and non-equilibrium processes [1-5]. But this assumption needs to be justified. For this, it is necessary to draw up a mathematical model of the considered process, determine the internal diffusion and effective diffusion coefficients, the characteristic mass transfer of the target component in the pores and intergranular phase, and compare them to draw a conclusion about the nature of the process. Thus, the purpose of the research is to develop a one-dimensional internal diffusion model of the dynamics of the non-equilibrium isothermal adsorption of sulfur compounds in the immobile layer of zeolites for the case that the adsorbent grains are monoporous, and to determine the mechanism that confirms the previously proposed assumption that the adsorption is characterized by internal diffusion based on experimental evidence. In this case, one of the important problems is to find a way to solve the equations of the mathematical model, as well as to identify the parameters in EHM using experimental materials [5-8]. Based on the study of the physico-chemical properties of the non-equilibrium internal diffusion isothermal adsorption process, its mathematical model was developed. The model of the process in the adsorber is built on the principle of considering the processes in the intragranular and intergranular phase together, which are described by the following equations.

1. Balance equation

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} + \vartheta \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} + m \frac{\partial a}{\partial t} = D_g \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2}. \tag{1}$$

Internal diffusion (grains are spherical) equation:

$$\frac{\partial C_c}{\partial t} = D_c \left(\frac{\partial^2 C_c}{\partial r^2} + \frac{2}{r} * \frac{\partial C_c}{\partial r} \right). \tag{2}$$

According to the Fick equation, the diffusion rate equation in the grain :

$$\frac{\partial a}{\partial t} = 4\pi R^2 N D_c \left(\frac{\partial C_c}{\partial r} \right)_{r=R} \tag{3}$$

For the solution of the system of equations (1-3), the following initial and boundary equation conditions of the diffusion rate equation in the grain are taken into account: $t=0, C(x, 0)=0, Q(r,0)=0, a(x, 0)=0; C(0, t)=C_0$ when $x=0$; When $x=L, C(L, t)=C_k$; When $r=R$

$$C_c(R, t) = C(x, t), \tag{4}$$

$r=0$ (symmetry condition).

$$\frac{\partial C_c}{\partial t} |_{r=0} = 0,$$

here C_c – grain cycles events adsorbent inside firmness;

D_c – diffusion coefficient within the pores of the granules;

r – radial coordinate of grain;

R – grain radius;

C – concentration of adsorbent in the moving phase;

D_g – effective diffusion coefficient in the intergranular phase;

ϑ – linear velocity of natural gas flow;

a – concentration of adsorbate;

N – the number of grains per unit volume.

$$N = \frac{n}{V} = \frac{(1-m)}{1/6\pi d^3}; n = \frac{V(1-m)}{1/6\pi d^3}$$

here d – grain diameter;

V – volume of adsorbent layer;

n – the number of grains in the volume V of the adsorbent layer.

$$m = \frac{1-m}{m'}$$

here m' – porosity of adsorbent layer;

L – the height of the adsorbent layer.

The system of differential equations (1-3) is an initial-boundary problem. As mentioned, the choice of the method of solving the differential equations (1-3) is of great importance. Experience shows that the numerical solution of this complex system with simultaneous determination of its parameters (they are not always constant) takes a lot of time. Therefore, in our choice, we gave the solution of these equations using experimental evidence, along with the identification of parameters in EHM, by analytical method, which allows to get the numerical values of internal diffusion coefficient D_g . To solve the system (1-3) considering the conditions (3H), the operator method – Laplace-Carson [8] transformation was applied. As a result, the opposites of the functions C_c , a , C were obtained in the following way:

$$C_{cs} = \frac{R \operatorname{Sh}(S_D r)}{r \operatorname{Sh}(S_D R)} C_s, \quad (5)$$

$$a_s = \frac{4\pi R^2 N D_c}{S} \left[S_D C \operatorname{th}(S_D R) - \frac{1}{r} \right] C_s, \quad (6)$$

$$C_s = C_0 \exp \left[\frac{1 - (1 + 4D_e A/v)}{2D_e/v} x \right], \quad (7)$$

here

$$A = \frac{S}{v} + \frac{m4\pi R^2 ND_c}{v} \left[S_D Cth(S_D R) - \frac{1}{R} \right]$$

$$S_D = \sqrt{\frac{S}{D_c}}$$

here S – transformation parameter;

$$C_1 = 1/2.89t;$$

$$S_2 = 3S_1;$$

$$S_3 = 5S_1.$$

The transition from the inverses of the functions (5-7) to the original is carried out by the method known in the literature [7]. The function relating the inverse and the original is as follows:

$$C_c = 0.9 \left[-C_{cS}(S_1) + \frac{16}{3} C_{cS}(S_2) - \frac{16}{5} C_{cS}(S_3) \right] \tag{8}$$

$$a = 0.9 \left[-a_S(S_1) + \frac{16}{3} a_S(S_2) - \frac{16}{5} a_S(S_3) \right] \tag{9}$$

$$C = 0.9 \left[-C_S(S_1) + \frac{16}{3} C_S(S_2) - \frac{16}{5} C_S(S_3) \right] \tag{10}$$

Internal diffusion D_c and the effective coefficient of diffusion D_g showed that the process has the nature of internal diffusion, so that the slow stage of the process is internal diffusion, because the value of D_c -mn is incomparably smaller than the value of Z. For a bed of immobile granular adsorbent, there is practically no displacement of matter in the opposite direction of flow at high flow rates. However, at very low flow velocities, back diffusion becomes important. Therefore, the adsorption process in immobile adsorbent layered adsorbents is adequately described by the ideal compression model at high flow rates (diffusion along the radius of the adsorber is not taken into account, more precisely, $D_r = 0$). The next issue is to determine the numerical values of D_c and D_g coefficients, which we tried to solve with the help of existing independent methods. To determine the value of the diffusion coefficient by a known method, the following expressions of dimensionless criteria from literature sources were used. It is known from [8] that:

$$Nu = \frac{\beta_0 d_2}{D}; R_e = \frac{v d}{\nu} \tag{11}$$

$$\text{When } 5 < Re < 80, Nu = 0.81 - Re^{0.4} \tag{12}$$

$$\text{When } 80 < Re < 5000, Nu = 0.695 - Re^{0.46} \tag{13}$$

t is known from [7].

$$t = \frac{b}{E} \ln[F(E_0 + F)] \left(a_\infty + \frac{F}{E} \right) - \frac{b a}{E} \quad (14)$$

(considered for a steady state of equilibrium: $C = C_0$), here

$$E = -\beta_0(C_0 b + 1), F = \beta_0 C_0 b a_\infty \quad (15)$$

$$a = \frac{a_\infty b C_p}{1 + b C_p} \quad (16)$$

b – Langmur's adsorption constant (for its precise determination, we use the method of least squares); a , w - saturated adsorption density in the solid phase; a - current adsorption density; ν - kinematic viscosity of gas (cm²/sec); C_p – equilibrium concentration of adsorbent; p_0 – kinetic coefficient. D_g and j_0 are calculated by substituting experimentally obtained values of quantities in formulas (11-16). However, calculating those parameters using this method known from the literature leads to wrong results. For example, with this method, we get the numerical value of the effective coefficient of diffusion $D_g = 3.051 \cdot 10^5$ cm² /sec, which is much smaller than the value of the internal diffusion coefficient D_c . This means that the process takes place in the external diffusion region. However, since the German value of D_g does not satisfy equations (8-10), this is not true. Therefore, this value of D_g is not adequate to the experimental evidence, rather, the determination of the parameters by the known method, that is, with the help of expressions (11-16), is not always justified. Thus, we come to the following conclusion: using the parameters obtained by the independent method does not satisfy the adequacy, as the calculation and comparison of the experimental values of the functions C and a give large difference. In this case, the identification of the parameters of the model using the system of equations (8) and empirical evidence is a more appropriate method, which is explained below.

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